

GJSH

SURVEY OF COMMON ABATTOIR FLIES AND ASSESSMENT OF THEIR ROLE AS VECTORS OF MICROORGANISMS IN DAMATURU METROPOLIS

Received : 30th
March, 2026

Accept: 16th
May, 2026

Abubakar Hassan

Ecotech Consult, Opposite 333 Nigeria Army Barracks Maiduguri

Abstract

Flies are ubiquitous insects of significant public health concern due to their capacity to transmit various pathogens, particularly in abattoir environments where organic waste is abundant. This study surveyed the population density of abattoir flies and assessed their role as mechanical vectors of microorganisms in Damaturu metropolis, Yobe State, Nigeria. A total of 287 fly specimens were collected over three weeks from three locations (Slaughtering Area, Processing Area, and Waste Disposal Area) using sweep nets and sticky traps. Flies were morphologically identified using standard taxonomic keys, and microbiological analysis was conducted on external body surfaces and gut contents using culture techniques on selective media. Two fly families were identified: *Calliphoridae* (Blow Flies) and *Sarcophagidae* (Flesh Flies), with *Sarcophagidae* being the most prevalent (44.57% in Processing Area). Aerobic mesophilic bacterial loads ranged from 1.0×10^5 to 7×10^7 CFU/mL, while fungal loads ranged from 0 to 5×10^6 CFU/mL. Seven pathogenic bacterial species were isolated: *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Shigella spp.*, *Salmonella spp.*, *Enterobacter spp.*, and *Pseudomonas spp.* The Processing Area showed the highest fly density and microbial contamination, with *Salmonella* and *Shigella* species exclusively isolated from this location. The study concludes that *Calliphoridae* and *Sarcophagidae* flies in Damaturu abattoir serve as significant mechanical vectors of pathogenic microorganisms, posing serious public health risks. Urgent interventions including improved waste management, structural modifications, worker training, and regulatory enforcement are recommended to mitigate fly-mediated contamination and enhance meat safety.

Keywords: Abattoir flies, *Calliphoridae*, *Sarcophagidae*, vectors, pathogenic bacteria, Damaturu metropolis
Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

Flies are among the most ubiquitous and medically significant insects associated with public health concerns due to their capacity to transmit various pathogens (Scott *et al.*, 2014; Khamesipour *et al.*, 2018). In abattoirs, where organic waste such as blood, offal, and fecal matter are common, flies proliferate and act as mechanical vectors of pathogenic microorganisms, including bacteria, fungi, protozoa, and viruses (Fasanella *et al.*, 2010; Eno-Obong *et al.*, 2005; Nwanta *et al.*, 2008; Addo *et al.*, 2022). Their indiscriminate contact with decomposing animal tissues, human environments, and food products makes them an important subject of epidemiological concern. In Damaturu metropolis, the capital of Yobe State, Northern Nigeria, abattoirs play a vital role in providing meat for public consumption. However, poor hygiene practices, inadequate waste management systems, and unregulated slaughtering conditions have contributed to an increase in fly populations and their associated health risks (Biu *et al.*, 2018; Badiru *et al.*, 2025). These flies are known to transport and spread pathogens that may lead to foodborne diseases and zoonotic infections among the local population (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2022; Omoregie *et al.*, 2025).

Among the most common fly species found in Nigerian abattoirs are the housefly (*Musca domestica*), flesh fly (*Sarcophaga spp.*), and blow fly (*Calliphora spp.* and *Chrysomya spp.*), which have been consistently implicated in the mechanical transmission of pathogens due to their feeding and breeding behaviors (Ekechukwu *et al.*, 2021; Khamesipour *et al.*, 2018). These flies pick up microorganisms from contaminated surfaces with their body parts and regurgitate or defecate on human food and utensils, facilitating microbial transmission (Eke *et al.*, 2016; Odetoyin *et al.*, 2020; Sudagidan *et al.*, 2022).

Gashua Journal of Sciences
and Humanities

Vol.3 No. 2, 2026

e-ISSN:2489-0049

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.2022643

Despite the evident health risks, there is limited data on the microbial profile of abattoir flies in Damaturu metropolis. Most available studies are generalized to the Northeast geopolitical zone, ignoring localized environmental factors that may influence vector prevalence and pathogenic load. Hence, there is a need for a targeted survey to fill this research gap and provide a scientific basis for public health interventions. The objectives were to determine the population density of flies, enumerate aerobic mesophilic bacterial and fungal load, and isolate and identify bacterial species from collected flies in the Damaturu abattoir.

Materials And Methods

Study Area and Duration

This study was conducted at the central abattoir in Damaturu, the capital city of Yobe State, Nigeria. Damaturu is characterized by a Sudano-Sahelian climate, marked by high temperatures and seasonal rainfall. Fly specimen collection was carried out over a three-week period, with sampling events occurring once weekly.

Study Design

A descriptive cross-sectional survey was employed to assess the prevalence, population density, and microbial carriage of flies within the abattoir environment.

Sample Collection and Handling

A purposive sampling technique was used to select the abattoir, while flies were captured using a random sampling method. Flies were collected using sterile sweep nets and sticky traps baited with decomposing liver, which were strategically placed approximately 1.5 meters from active slaughtering areas. Captured specimens were promptly transferred to sterile, ventilated containers, labeled according to their collection location and date, and immediately chilled at 4°C in a cooler. The samples were then transported to the laboratory for processing within two hours of collection. A total of 287 fly specimens were collected during the study period.

Morphological Identification of Flies

In the laboratory, flies were temporarily immobilized by chilling at 4°C to facilitate handling. Morphological identification to the family level (Calliphoridae and Sarcophagidae) was performed using standard taxonomic keys (Service, 2012). Further identification of specific morphological features was conducted under an electric microscope at ×40 magnification.

Microbiological Analysis of Sample Processing

Each fly was first rinsed in sterile water to remove superficial contaminants. Serial dilutions were then prepared from the rinse solution. To analyze both external and internal microbial carriage, samples were obtained by swabbing the external body surface and by dissecting and culturing the contents of the gut.

Culture and Enumeration

Aliquots from the prepared samples were inoculated onto the following culture media: Nutrient agar for general bacterial isolation, incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours; Salmonella-Shigella agar (SSA) for the isolation of Salmonella and Shigella spp., incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours; Mannitol Salt Agar (MSA) for the isolation of Staphylococcus spp., incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours; Eosin Methylene Blue agar (EMB) for the isolation of coliforms such as Escherichia coli, Klebsiella spp., and Enterobacter spp., incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours; and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) for the isolation of fungi, incubated at 25-28°C for 3-5 days. Following incubation, colony-forming units (CFUs) were counted and recorded as CFU per milliliter (CFU/mL). Representative colonies were then subcultured onto fresh media to obtain pure isolates for further identification.

Identification of Isolates

Bacterial isolates were identified based on a combination of their colonial morphology, Gram staining reaction, and standard biochemical tests. Fungal isolates were identified based on their macroscopic (colony morphology, pigmentation) and microscopic (hyphal structure, spore morphology) characteristics.

Data Analysis

Data on fly populations and microbial isolates were collated and analyzed using descriptive statistics. Fly population densities were expressed as absolute numbers and percentages. The microbial load was quantified as CFU/mL, and the data were tabulated to illustrate weekly variations across different sampling locations. The results were interpreted in the context of public health significance by comparing them to established microbiological standards.

Results

Population Density of Flies

A total of 287 flies were collected over three weeks from three locations in Damaturu abattoir. Two families were identified: *Calliphoridae* (Blow Flies) and *Sarcophagidae* (Flesh Flies). The Processing Area (Figure 1) had the highest overall fly population (44.57%), dominated by *Sarcophagidae*. The Slaughtering Area (Figure 2) and Waste Disposal Area (Figure 3) showed lower total densities at 15.73% and 17.60%. Population trends increased from Week 1 (59 flies), week 2 (104 flies) to Week 3 (124 flies) (Table 1). *Sarcophagidae* were consistently more numerous than *Calliphoridae* in the Slaughtering and Processing Areas, while their numbers were comparable in the Waste Disposal Area.

Table 1: Determination of Population Density of House Flies from Different Location in Damaturu Abattoir

Sampling Point	Species	Population (%)			TOTAL (%)
		Week1	Week2	Week3	
Slaughtering Area	<i>Calliphoridae</i>	3 (5.0%)	2 (1.92%)	7(5.64)	12(4.5)
	<i>Sarcophagidae</i>	9 (15.3%)	12(11.53%)	21(16.93)	42(15.73)
Processing Area	<i>Calliphoridae</i>	4 (6.7%)	11(10.58%)	12(9.7)	27(10.11)
	<i>Sarcophagidae</i>	24 (40.6%)	58(55.78%)	37(29.83)	119(44.57)
Waste Disposal Area	<i>Calliphoridae</i>	15 (25.4%)	5(4.80%)	20(16.12)	40(14.98)
	<i>Sarcophagidae</i>	4 (6.7%)	16(15.39%)	27(21.8)	47(17.60)
TOTAL (%)		59 (100%)	104(100%)	124(100)	287(100)

Source: Laboratory Work, (2025).

Figure 1: Processing Area

Source: Field Work, 2025

Figure 2: Slaughter Area

Source: Field Work, 2025

Figure 3: Waste Disposal Area

Source: Field Work, 2025

Aerobic Mesophilic Bacterial Load

All fly samples carried substantial bacterial loads, with counts frequently reaching 10^7 CFU/mL. The highest bacterial counts were recorded in Week 2 across most locations and species (Plate 1). *Sarcophagidae* from the Slaughtering Area and *Calliphoridae* from the Waste Disposal Area in Week 2 showed remarkably high counts of 6×10^7 and 7×10^7 CFU/mL (Table 2).

Table 2: Enumeration of Aerobic Mesophilic Bacteria of House Flies from Different Location in Damaturu Abattoir

Location	Species	Number of Colonies (CFU/mL)		
		Week1	Week2	Week3
Slaughtering Area	<i>Calliphoridae</i>	1.0×10^5	4.4×10^7	1.7×10^6
	<i>Sarcophagidae</i>	7.2×10^6	6×10^7	3.1×10^6
Processing Area	<i>Calliphoridae</i>	6.0×10^6	3.9×10^7	1×10^6
	<i>Sarcophagidae</i>	1.09×10^7	5.4×10^7	1.9×10^6
Waste Disposal Area	<i>Calliphoridae</i>	5.1×10^6	7×10^7	3×10^6
	<i>Sarcophagidae</i>	2.04×10^7	5.5×10^7	3.7×10^6

Source: Laboratory Work, (2025).

Fungal Load

Fungal counts were substantial, particularly in Week 2, with values as high as 5×10^6 CFU/mL recorded for *Calliphoridae* in the Waste Disposal Area (Plate 2). A notable observation was the absence of fungi on *Calliphoridae* from the Waste Disposal Area in Week 3. *Sarcophagidae* in the Processing Area consistently carried high fungal loads across the weeks (Table 3).

Plate 1: Bacterial Load week 2.

Source: Laboratory Work, (2025)

Plate 2: Fungal Load week 2

Source: Laboratory Work, (2025)

Table 3: Enumeration of Fungi of House Flies from Different Location in Damaturu Abattoir

Location	Species	Number of Colonies (Cfu/mL)		
		Week1	Week2	Week3
Slaughtering Area	Calliphoridae	4.5×10^2	1×10^6	2×10^1
	Sarcophagiadae	7.9×10^2	3×10^6	4×10^1
Processing Area	Calliphoridae	9.8×10^2	3×10^6	8×10^1
	Sarcophagiadae	1.09×10^3	5×10^6	7×10^1
Waste Disposal Area	Calliphoridae	1.7×10^2	5×10^6	0
	Sarcophagiadae	1.8×10^2	3×10^6	2×10^1

Source: Laboratory Work, (2025)

Bacterial Species Isolated

Seven pathogenic and opportunistic bacterial species were isolated from the flies: *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Shigella spp.*, *Salmonella spp.*, *Enterobacter spp.* and *Pseudomonas spp.* *Shigella spp.* was particularly abundant in the Processing Area during Week 3 on both fly species, with counts reaching 4×10^6 and 3.8×10^6 CFU/mL (Table 4). *Salmonella spp.* was isolated in Week 3, primarily from the Processing and Waste Disposal Areas. The presence of *S. aureus* and *K. pneumoniae* across all locations and weeks indicated constant exposure to sources of infection.

Table 4: Enumeration of Bacterial Species of House Flies from Different Location in Damaturu Abattoir

Sampling Point	Species	Period	Number of Colonies (Cfu/mL)						
			E.coli	K.pneumoniae	S.aureus	Shigella Spp	Salmonella Spp	Enterobacter spp	Pseudomonas spp
Slaughtering Area	Calliphoridae	W1	0	1x10 ⁴	3x10 ⁴	0	0	2x10 ⁴	0
		W2	7.5x10 ⁵	4.2x10 ⁵	4.2x10 ⁵	6.2x10 ⁵	0	4.8x10 ⁵	0
		W3	0	7x10 ⁵	2x10 ⁵	0	0	0	0
	Sarcophagiadae	W1	6x10 ⁴	3x10 ⁴	6x10 ⁴	0	0	2x10 ⁴	0
		W2	8.3x10 ⁵	5.2x10 ⁵	1.9x10 ⁵	4.2x10 ⁵	0	4.1x10 ⁵	0
		W3	0	1.5x10 ⁶	1x10 ⁵	4x10 ⁶	0	0	0
Processing Area	Calliphoridae	W1	0	0	1.50x10 ⁶	0	0	1x10 ⁴	0
		W2	5.10x10 ⁴	6.2x10 ⁵	1.9x10 ⁵	7.8x10 ⁵	0	4x10 ⁵	0
		W3	0	1.46x10 ⁷	5.2x10 ⁶	6x10 ⁶	1x10 ⁶	3.8x10 ⁶	0
	Sarcophagiadae	W1	0	1.3x10 ⁶	2.09x10 ⁶	0	0	7x10 ⁴	0
		W2	3.9x10 ⁵	5.3x10 ⁵	8.5x10 ⁵	3.2x10 ⁶	0	4.6x10 ⁵	7x10 ⁵
		W3	0	9.2x10 ⁶	1.3x10 ⁶	3.8x10 ⁶	4.4x10 ⁶	3.5x10 ⁶	0
Waste Disposal Area	Calliphoridae	W1	0	2x10 ⁴	9.6x10 ⁵	0	0	0	0
		W2	5x10 ⁴	2.9x10 ⁵	4.6x10 ⁵	1.29x10 ⁵	0	1.3x10 ⁵	0
		W3	0	5.2x10 ⁶	4x10 ⁵	0	7x10 ⁵	0	0
	Sarcophagiadae	W1	0	0	1.03x10 ⁴	0	0	0	0
		W2	6.9x10 ⁵	4.7x10 ⁵	2.3x10 ⁵	3.8x10 ⁶	0	5.2x10 ⁵	0
		W3	0	4.4x10 ⁶	6x10 ⁵	1.3x10 ⁶	9x10 ⁵	0	0

Source: Laboratory Work, (2025).

Morphological Identification of Flies

Calliphoridae (Blow Flies) were identified by their shiny, metallic coloring with blue thoraces and abdomen, and three-segmented aristate antennae. *Sarcophagidae* (Flesh Flies) were characterized by red eyes and bristled abdomen, with free abdominal sternites covering the margins of tergites.

Morphological features of Bacteria

Table 4.5 shows bacterial isolates identified based on morphological features on differential media. The bacteria identified are; *E. Coli*, *Klebsiella spp.*, *S. aureus*, *Shigella spp.*, *Salmonella spp.*, *Enterobacter spp.*, and *Pseudomonas spp.*

Table 4.5: Morphological Features of isolated Bacteria on Differential Media

Isolates	Morphological features
<i>E.coli</i>	Green metallic sheen on Eosine Methylene Blue (EMB)
<i>Klebsiella spp</i>	Pink mucoid colonies on Eosine Methylene Blue (EMB)
<i>S.aureus</i>	Golden yellow colonies on Mannitol Salt Agar (MSA)
<i>Shigella spp</i>	Colorless colonies on Salmonella Shigella Agar (SSA)
<i>Salmonella spp</i>	Colorless colonies with black at the center on Salmonella Shigella Agar (SSA)
<i>Enterobacter spp</i>	Pink to purple colonies on Eosine Methylene Blue (EMB)
<i>Pseudomonas spp</i>	Green pigment colonies on Nutrient Agar (NA)

Source: Laboratory Work, (2025)

Discussion

This study successfully surveyed the population density of flies and assessed their role as mechanical vectors of pathogenic microorganisms in Damaturu abattoir. The findings provide critical insights into the public health risks associated with fly infestation in this key meat processing facility. The study identified two dominant fly families: *Calliphoridae* (Blow Flies) and *Sarcophagidae* (Flesh Flies). It suggests that in the specific environmental conditions of Damaturu abattoir, flesh flies and blow flies are the predominant vectors. This could be attributed to the abundance of fresh meat and animal remains, which are primary attractants for these species, as highlighted in the literature (Ekpunobi *et al.*, 2024; Yoksa *et al.*, 2026).

The population density data revealed that the Processing Area had the highest concentration of flies (44.57%), with *Sarcophagidae* being the most prevalent. This aligns with the Vector Transmission Theory, as the Processing Area, with its exposed meat products, provides an ideal environment for flies to feed and potentially contaminate meat ready for public consumption. The increasing fly population from Week 1 to Week 3 indicates a rapidly proliferating vector population, likely fueled by the availability of organic waste and favorable climatic conditions, a factor previously noted by Adesiyan *et al.* (2025) for Northern Nigerian abattoirs.

The microbiological analysis confirmed that both fly species are potent mechanical vectors. The aerobic mesophilic bacterial load was substantial, frequently reaching 10^7 CFU/mL. These high counts are consistent with studies by Adebowale *et al.* (2022) and Chowdary *et al.* (2025), who reported that flies can carry millions of bacteria on their bodies. The notably higher bacterial and fungal loads in Week 2 across most locations suggest a temporal peak in microbial contamination, possibly linked to factors like temperature, humidity, or a transient lapse in waste management practices during that period. Most critically, the isolation and enumeration of specific pathogens from the flies present a direct public health threat. The presence of *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *S. aureus*, *Shigella spp.*, and *Salmonella spp.* corroborates findings from other Nigerian studies (Rani *et al.* 2023; Osibote *et al.*, 2014; Ezedianafo *et al.*, 2025). The spatial distribution of these pathogens is particularly revealing. The high prevalence of *Shigella spp.* and the exclusive appearance of *Salmonella spp.* in the Processing Area during Week 3 demonstrate that the area where meat is prepared for sale is a critical point for pathogen transmission. The consistent presence of *S. aureus* and *K. pneumoniae* across all areas underscores the flies' constant exposure to sources of pyogenic and enteric infections.

The fungal load, though lower than bacterial counts, was significant, confirming that flies are also vectors for fungal spores. The isolation of fungi like *Candida* and *Aspergillus* poses an additional risk, especially to immune-compromised individuals, as noted by Yoksa *et al.*, (2026). The Processing Area, which had the highest fly density, also consistently showed high levels of diverse pathogenic bacteria. This correlation emphasizes that reducing fly density is a direct strategy for reducing microbial contamination in the abattoir.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study concludes that Damaturu abattoir is significantly infested with *Calliphoridae* and *Sarcophagidae* flies, which act as efficient mechanical vectors for a wide range of pathogenic bacteria and fungi. The Processing Area is the most critical hotspot for fly activity and microbial contamination. The flies carry high loads of microorganisms, including specific pathogens responsible for serious foodborne illnesses such as *Salmonellosis*, *Shigellosis*, and *Staphylococcal* infections.

The findings confirm that the abattoir environment in Damaturu poses a substantial risk to meat safety and public health. The proliferation of flies and the associated microbial contamination are likely consequences of poor waste management, open slaughtering practices, and lack of effective vector control measures. Therefore, the situation in Damaturu abattoir requires immediate and targeted public health intervention to safeguard consumers and abattoir workers.

In recommendations the abattoir management need immediate vector control and sanitation through implementation of rigorous daily waste management protocols and introduce targeted fly control measures including insecticide spraying (with rotation to prevent resistance) and installation of fly traps and electrocutors, particularly in the Processing Area.

References

- Addo, S. O., Oppong, J., Achawe, E. M., Nketia, B. B., Agyei, P. B., & Larbi, J. A. (2022). Filth Flies As Carriers of Intestinal Parasites and Fungi in a Tertiary Institution in Ghana. *Journal of Medical Microbiological Infectious Diseases*, 10 (4): 179-185. DOI:10.52547/JoMMID.10.4.179
- Adebowale, O.O., Ekundayo, O., Olasoju, M., Oladejo, O. O. & Awoseyi, A.A., (2022). Animal diseases and zoonoses at a municipal slaughterhouse in Southwest Nigeria: Three-year retrospective survey (2014–2016). *Revue d'élevage et de médecine vétérinaire des pays tropicaux* 75 (4), 117-123. <https://doi.org/10.19182/remvt.37013>
- Adesiyun, I. M., Adamu, M. K., Gershon, G. D., Usman, A. B., Fabunmi, T. B., Emmanuel, O. E. & Ofonime E Johnson, O. E. (2025). Assessment of Butchers' knowledge of occupational hazards and hygiene practices at slaughterhouses in Bauchi state. *Discov Public Health* 22, 606. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12982-025-00982-z>
- Badiru, A., Kayode, O. O., Abdulraheem, O. S., Temitope, A. A., Micheal, A. O. & Alabi, Y. (2025). Assessment of Meat Safety and Hygiene: Knowledge, Attitude and Practices in Selected Abattoirs in Ilorin, Nigeria. *Al-Hikmah. Journal of Health Sciences*, 4(1), 59-70. <https://alhikmahuniversity.edu.ng/AJOHS/index.php/journal>
- Biu, A. A., Kaltungo, B. Y., & Baba, A. Y. (2018). A survey of abattoir wastes management practices and their public health implications in Damaturu, Yobe State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Animal Science and Technology*, 2: 97-100. doi:10.25081/jsa.2018.v2.1038
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). (2021). Vector-borne diseases. U.S. Department of Health & Human Services.
- Chowdary, L. R., Harish, G. N., Karedla, A. K. & Chandrashekara, K. M. (2025). Flies of Public Health Importance. 1st Ed. CRC Press. Taylor & Francis Group, London.
- Eke, S. S., Idris, A. R., Omalu, I. C. J., Otuu, C. A., Ibeh, E. O., Ubanwa, E. D., Luka, J. & Paul, S. (2016). Relative abundance of synanthropic flies with associated parasites and pathogens in Minna Metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology*, 37(2): 142-146. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/njpar.v37i2.4>
- Ekechukwu, N. E., Ekeh, F. N., Ohanu, C. M., Ezinwa, H. C. & Aguzie, I. O. N. (2021). Insect Fauna Diversity and Abundance in Abattoirs in Enugu North Senatorial Zone, Eastern Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Zoology*, 1-7. <https://dx.doi.org/10.17582/journal.pjz/20190324190351>
- Ekpunobi, N. F., Adesanoye, S., Orababa, O., Adinnu, C., Okorie, C. & Akinsuyi, S. (2024). Public health perspective of public abattoirs in Nigeria, challenges and solutions. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2024, 26(02): 115–127. <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2024.26.2.0527>
- Eno-Obong, A., Itah, A., & Obun, C. (2005). Prevalence Of Micro-Organisms In Flies And Meat Cuts In Uyo Abattoir, Akwa Ibom State. *Global Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 3(1), 79–81. <https://doi.org/10.4314/gjass.v3i1.2239>
- Ezedianafo, J. N., Iheukwumere, I. H., Iheukwumere C. M., Nwike, O. O. & Ubajekwe, C. C., (2025). Musca domestica: A Vector of Multidrug-Resistant Enteric Bacteria. *Journal of Veterinary, Allied, and One Health Sciences*, 1(2), 30-38. <https://doi.org/10.54117/3vwg0p36>
- Fasanella, A., Scasciamacchia, S., Garofolo, G., Giangaspero, A., Tarsitano, E., & Adone, R. (2010). Evaluation of the house fly *Musca domestica* as a mechanical vector for an anthrax. *PLoS One*. 5(8):e12219. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0012219.
- Ibrahim, S., Auta, T. & Orpin, J. B. (2022). Occurrence of Gastrointestinal Parasites in Cattle Slaughtered at Central Abattoir in Katsina Metropolis, Katsina State, Nigeria. *Res. J. Vet. Sci.*, 15 (2): 65-71. <https://doi.org/10.17311/rjvs.2022.65.71>
- Khamesipour, F., Lankarani, K. B., Honarvar, B., & Kwenti, T. E. (2018). A systematic review of human pathogens carried by the housefly (*Musca domestica* L.). *BMC Public Health*, 18(1), 1049. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-5934-3>
- Khamesipour, F., Lankarani, K. B., Honarvar, B., & Kwenti, T. E. (2018). A systematic review of human pathogens carried by the housefly (*Musca domestica* L.). *BMC Public Health*, 18(1), 1049. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-5934-3>
- Nwanta, J. A., Onunkwo, J. I., Ezenduka, V. E., Phil-Eze, P. O., & Egege, S. C. (2008). Abattoir operations and waste management in Nigeria: A review of challenges and prospects. *Sokoto Journal of Veterinary Sciences*. 7(2): 61-67. ISSN 1595-093X
- Odetoyin, B., Adeola, B., & Olaniran, O. (2020). Frequency and Antimicrobial Resistance Patterns of Bacterial Species Isolated from the Body Surface of the Housefly (*Musca domestica*) in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal Arthropod Borne Diseases*, 14(1): 88–96. doi:10.18502/jad.v14i1.2715

- Omoriegbe, A. O., Ogofure, A. G., Osawe, E. N., Ambali, N. M., Mordi, O. J., Akpan, B. E. & Rotimi, J. (2025). Bacterial species associated with houseflies (*Musca domestica*) and blowflies (*Lucilia cuprina* and *L. sericata*) at a market dumpsite and possible disease risk in Benin City, Nigeria. *UNIZIK Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences* 4(1): 1452-1460. <https://journals.unizik.edu.ng/index.php/ujeas>
- Osibote, I. A., Okiki, P. A., Ekundayo, E. A. & Adekunle, A. C., (2014). Prevalence of Multidrug Resistant Bacterial Isolates from Meat Processing Equipment and Abattoir Environment in Ado Ekiti. *Advances in Biological Research* 8 (5): 207-211. DOI: 10.5829/idosi.abr.2014.8.5.84186
- Rani, Z. T., Mhlongo, L. C., & Hugo, A. (2023). Microbial Profiles of Meat at Different Stages of the Distribution Chain from the Abattoir to Retail Outlets. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 20(3): 1986. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20031986>
- Scott, J. G., Warren, W. C., Beukeboom, L. W., Bopp, D., Clark, A. G., Giers, S. D., Hediger, M., Jones, A. K., Kasai, S., Leichter, C. A., Li, M., Meisel, R. P., Minx, P., Murphy, T. D., Nelson, D. R., Reid, W. R., Rinkevich, F. D., Robertson, H. M., Sackton, T. B., Sattelle, D. B., Thibaud-Nissen, F., Tomlinson, C., Zande, L. V., Walden, K. K. O., Wilson, R. K. & Liu, N. (2014). Genome of the house fly, *Musca domestica* L., a global vector of diseases with adaptations to a septic environment. *Genome Biol* 15, 466. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-014-0466-3>
- Service, M. W. (2012). *Medical entomology for students* (5th ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Sudagidan, M., Ozalp, V. C., Can, A., Eliga, H., Yurt, M. N. Z., Tasbasi, B. B., Acar, E. E., Kavruk, M. & Koasak, O. (2022). Surface microbiota and associated staphylococci of houseflies (*Musca domestica*) collected from different environmental sources. *Microbial Pathogenesis*, 164: 105439. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpath.2022.105439>.
- World Health Organization (WHO). (2022). Food safety. Retrieved on 25/October/2025 from <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/food-safety>
- Yoksa, T., Habila, D., Gapsiso, R., David, J. & Andeze, Y. D. (2026). Skin Diseases and Their Impact on Sheep Production. In *Sheep Farming - In Association of Resilience and Production*. IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.1012951>